

Progress report from Working Group 1

Scoping the Needs of Open Science Monitoring

(Reporting period: 2025)

1. General information

Co-chairs:

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Initial objectives:

WG1 was established to examine the foundations of Open Science (OS) monitoring within the Open Science Monitoring Initiative (OSMI). Its objectives are to:

1. map key stakeholders and beneficiaries affected by Open Science at international, national, and local levels.
2. explore the scope of Open Science monitoring and clarify what should be monitored and why; and
3. identify areas requiring quantitative, qualitative, or mixed methods to effectively support Open Science monitoring.

2. Summary of the group's activities since its creation

WG1's work in 2025 focused on **scoping, needs identification, and conceptual alignment**, rather than indicator production. Activities combined collective brainstorming, structured subgroup work, and a global survey to capture community perspectives on monitoring needs, priorities, barriers, and methodological preferences.

A key outcome was the articulation of **monitoring as a system-level function**, intended to support learning, equity, and transformation, not solely compliance or reporting

3. Upcoming activities, deliverables, and timeline

WG1 held **four plenary meetings** in 2025:

- **8 May 2025**
- **5 June 2025**
- **31 July 2025**

- **25 September 2025**

Meetings were attended by WG1 members from multiple regions and professional roles. Participation fluctuated across subgroups, with challenges in sustained engagement noted in some thematic areas. These challenges directly informed the decision to complement subgroup work with a survey-based approach.

Key discussion points, methodologies, and outputs

Key discussion points

- Alignment of Open Science monitoring with the **UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science** and the **2025 Principles of Open Science Monitoring**.
- Risks of narrow, metric-driven monitoring reinforcing inequities.
- The need to distinguish between **policy adoption and policy implementation**.
- The importance of equity, context sensitivity, and mixed-method approaches.

Methodologies used

- Collective brainstorming mapped to UNESCO Open Science pillars.
- Subgroup discussions structured around five thematic areas, including a cross-cutting “Monitoring Foundations” theme.
- A global online survey (43 items) combining quantitative questions and open-ended responses, yielding **35 complete responses** across eight UNESCO regions.

Key outputs

- A scoping report documenting WG1’s conceptual work and survey findings.
- Empirical evidence on monitoring priorities, perceived beneficiaries, barriers, and methodological preferences.
- Early articulation of principles for a **modular, equity-sensitive monitoring framework**.

Key findings (high-level)

- Monitoring is currently used primarily for strategic planning and compliance, with a narrow focus on Open Access.
- Respondents strongly support expanding monitoring to include **Open and FAIR data, equity, reproducibility, research assessment, and societal engagement**.
- Benefits of Open Science are perceived as **unevenly distributed**, with well-resourced public institutions and Global North contexts seen as primary beneficiaries.

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- Major barriers include lack of incentives, governance gaps, cost constraints, and capacity limitations.
 - **Mixed-method approaches** are strongly preferred; only **26%** of proposed “essential” indicators were reported as fully measurable in current contexts

Upcoming activities, deliverables, and timeline

2026 planned activities

- Finalization of the WG1 report incorporating structured feedback from WG members.
- Development of a **conceptual modular monitoring framework**, building on survey findings and OSMI principles.
- Coordination with other OSMI Working Groups to ensure coherence and complementarity across frameworks.

Timeline

- **February 2026:** Internal WG1 review and revision of the draft report.
- **March 2026:** Presentation of progress and next steps to the OSMI Board.
- **Q2–Q3 2026:** Contribution to cross-WG discussions on framework design and implementation pathways.

